

Beyond the page: Enriching storybooks with embodied activities to improve mathematics skills – A scoping review

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ABSTRACT

Background: This article explores approaches to enriching storybook reading experiences to facilitate mathematics learning in children.

Method: A scoping review of existing literature was conducted to identify approaches for enhancing mathematics storybooks.

Results: Two primary approaches were identified: hands-on physical experiences, such as gestures, enactment, and manipulatives; and technology-driven interventions, such as augmented reality and wearables. Hands-on experiences can promote numerical understanding through multisensory interactions. Technology-driven approaches may alleviate mathematics anxiety and increase motivation. Both approaches can foster numeracy by increasing engagement with the learning content.

Conclusion: Integrating enriched activities into mathematics storybook reading has the potential to support numeracy development.

1. Introduction

The use of storybooks is a well-researched approach to fostering the development of literacy in early childhood [1]. Storybooks encompass text and visual illustrations and rely on the interplay between written story and illustrations; typically, both aspects are crafted with a deliberate aesthetic purpose in mind [2]. Good storybooks support reader-child activities and interactions between the reader and the child that facilitate the connections of prior and new knowledge [3]. Adult readers can guide children through a storybook in various ways and help children practice skills via interaction and playful activities [4].

This review is written from the perspective of researchers in education who work with theories of embodied cognition (see, e.g., [5]) and who also, more practically, work with teachers on building interactive educational tools for the learning of mathematics. As such, the present review is driven by our interest in the role of *interactions*—specifically physical interactions—in the apparent educational effectiveness of storybooks. Given our theoretical interest in embodied cognition, and our practical impetus to create useable educational tools, this paper takes a

closer look at mathematics storybooks, an existing, yet understudied educational tool that appears to capture both our theoretical and practical interests. More specifically, we ask: What are the different ways in which mathematics storybooks enable interactions? How are those interactions supported?

Before we focus on storybooks for mathematics learning, however, it may be helpful to address the pedagogical effectiveness of storybooks in a more researched subgenre, that of storybooks for literacy. As we shall see, research in this area highlights the importance of physical interactions.

1.1. Storybooks as educational tools for literacy

Numerous studies have highlighted the effectiveness of storybook reading for literacy acquisition and identified factors contributing to its success—for example, the quantity of storybook reading (i.e. more storybook reading leading to better letter naming, phonemic awareness, emergent literacy; [6]), but also dialogic reading approaches [7,8]. Dialogic reading goes beyond the mere narration of a story and involves

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strategies such as interacting with the story content, with the aim of directing a child's attention and stimulating active engagement. This kind of elevated engagement with the learning content in dialogic reading was observed to further increase the effectiveness of storybook reading.

In short, a core finding from research on storybooks for literacy is that these educational tools are more effective when engagement is enhanced, through meaningful interactions. These enhancements range from enacting aspects of the story through gestures (i.e., movements that express meaning, e.g., pointing to highlight or using hand movement to indicate magnitude) to incorporating multimedia elements (i.e., visual, audio, and music elements; [9]), augmented reality (i.e., technology that superimposes a generated image over the real world, see, e.g., [10]), and even the use of fully digital and interactive storybook designs, including embedded games [4] and wearables [11].

For example, the "Moved by Reading" intervention introduces embodied actions (i.e., physical movements and bodily actions) into the reading process. Children manipulate digital images or physically act out specific parts of the story by using toys like puppets to mimic a conversation between characters or recreate parts of the story. This intervention appears to enhance comprehension, story recall, positive affect, and focusing on relevant information [12,13].

1.2. Storybooks as educational tools for mathematics

While research on learning from storybooks tended to focus on the development of literacy (reading comprehension, e.g., [14]), some scholars have extended this research to other domains. Glenberg and colleagues, in particular, have consistently demonstrated that simulating actions during storybook reading can also enhance problem-solving skills in mathematics [12].

In comparison to storybooks for literacy, there is a smaller but growing interest in the beneficial effects of storybook reading on mathematics development (e.g., for a review of multisensory reading, see [15]). Accordingly, several studies have evaluated and demonstrated the effectiveness of storybook reading in fostering children's mathematics development [16–19]. A mathematics storybook incorporates mathematics concepts into its narrative, enabling children to engage with these concepts in the context of a story. Through storytelling and accompanying illustrations, children can explore mathematical ideas in an accessible and enjoyable way [20].

Mathematics storybooks cover not only basic topics like numbers, measurement, and geometry, but also broader concepts such as growth, patterns, fairness, and cause and effect [21]. Research indicates that these storybooks can significantly enhance children's mathematics development, especially when tailored to their prior knowledge and delivered in engaging ways [4,20,22,23]. For example, Gibson et al. [24] examined the effects of parent-led storybook reading on number word knowledge in more than children aged 2 to 4. Children were randomly assigned to one of three groups: a number storybook group, a non-numerical storybook group, and a business-as-usual control group. The study found that children in the number storybook group showed significantly greater gains in counting and number word knowledge compared to both control conditions.

Similarly, Van den Heuvel-Panhuizen et al. [19] conducted a large-scale classroom-based study with 384 kindergartners aged 4–6. The experimental group were read picture books covering number, measurement, and geometry topics over a three-month period and showed significantly more pronounced improvement in mathematical performance (as measured by a curriculum-based 25-item test assessing the three mathematical domains addressed in the picture books) compared to the control group who followed the regular kindergarten curriculum.

Importantly, beyond measurable skill gains, the narrative and visual elements of storybooks promote meaningful discussions. For example, illustrations can prompt children to compare sizes, count objects, or

recognize shapes embedded in the story context [25]. In classroom settings, teachers often use storybook prompts to ask questions such as "Which is longer?" or "How many are left?", encouraging children to verbalize their mathematical thinking [19]. Similarly, Flevares and Schiff [22] found that dialogic reading of storybooks supports the development of number sense and problem-solving skills by integrating math vocabulary into everyday storytelling. These findings underscore the potential of well-designed mathematics storybooks to foster both skill development and deeper conceptual understanding.

Given the effectiveness of storybooks for mathematics learning, it seems natural to ask whether learning from mathematics storybooks may also benefit from enhanced engagement, similar to what we saw in research on storybooks for literacy. Research on whether mathematics learning through storybooks could be enhanced using approaches proven effective for literacy is limited. Previous reviews emphasize the potential of integrating storybooks into mathematics education and propose criteria for selecting storybooks, as well as guidelines for instructional practices in early childhood education. Flevares and Schiff [22], for example, summarized findings from 11 intervention studies on using storybooks to facilitate mathematics development. Similarly, Op 't Eynde et al. [23] concluded that while storybook reading effectively supports basic numerical learning, it predominantly focuses on numbers and operations. They highlighted the lack of a standardized framework for "mathematics picture books" and emphasized the need for future studies to investigate the role of non-verbal communication, including gestures, in supporting mathematics learning.

Fig. 1

1.3. Enhancing interactions in storybooks for mathematics learning

Against this background, the current study aimed at identifying approaches and procedures to enhance interactions in the context of mathematics learning through storybook reading. A particular focus is placed on approaches that allow children to engage in embodied activities—physical actions directly related to the learning content. Embodied activities, such as gestures, movements, and manipulative interactions, engage the body in the learning process. This approach aligns with the theory of embodied cognition, which posits that cognitive concepts and processes are grounded in bodily experiences acquired through interactions with the world ([27]; Barsalou, 2018).

Moreover, accumulating evidence suggests that specific embodied experiences are crucial for the development of basic mathematical skills. For instance, fine motor skills, such as the ability to coordinate finger and hand movements for tasks like threading beads, have been functionally linked to basic mathematical abilities [28,29]. Specific embodied activities have also shown promise in facilitating numerical learning. These include walking along a number line to improve number comprehension [30,31], using proportional hand gestures while learning about proportions [32], and using fingers for counting and calculating [33,34].

Drawing on these insights, there is growing consensus among learning scientists that targeted embodied activities can bridge the gap between abstract mathematical concepts and concrete physical experiences, enhancing children's understanding [5]. Integrating these activities into storybooks is particularly appealing because storybooks provide a narrative framework where mathematical concepts can be embedded and enacted. By combining narrative-driven learning with embodied activities, we hypothesize that children's mathematical skills can be facilitated in a manner that is both engaging and effective, similar to how embodied approaches have successfully supported literacy acquisition [14].

While prior research has examined how embodied interactions enhance the impact of storybooks on early literacy development, the potential of these activities to support early mathematical learning remains underexplored. This scoping review addresses this gap by investigating whether interactive and embodied strategies, proven effective

Fig. 1. Examples of embodied interactions with mathematical storybooks. Through which the mathematical idea behind a story element is substantiated. Left: A child reenacts a story element on counting from *The Very Hungry Caterpillar* by Eric Carle [26] using toy peaches and a caterpillar figure, supporting the mathematical ideas of one-to-one correspondence and quantity recognition. Right: A story element about bridge-building introduces triangular structures, which the child reconstructs physically using sticks, highlighting the geometric mathematical idea behind the respective story element.

for literacy, can similarly benefit early mathematics learning. The novelty of this study lies in its focus on the intersection of narrative and embodied learning within the context of early mathematics learning. Through a systematic review of the literature, we aim to provide initial insights into how enhancing storybook reading with embodied methods can facilitate early mathematical skills. These findings are intended to serve as a foundation for future empirical research, advancing understanding and practice in this promising area.

2. Methods

This study followed the procedure of a scoping review [35], which is designed to map the existing literature on a broad topic and to identify key concepts, gaps, and types of evidence available. Unlike a systematic review, a scoping review is more exploratory in nature, aiming to provide an overview of a wide-ranging research area. The rationale for choosing this approach was to capture the full range of studies investigating how storybook reading as a means for facilitating early numerical development can be enriched (for instance, by embodied activities) without restricting the analysis to a narrow set of criteria.

Early mathematical competencies, as conceptualized in the model of early numerical development by Krajewski and Schneider [36], encompass a range of foundational skills that are critical building blocks for the development of more advanced mathematical abilities. These competencies include the ability to understand and manipulate numbers, counting, recognition of numerical relationships, and basic arithmetic operations. By focusing on competencies explicitly aligned with established models like Krajewski and Schneider's, our review ensures a more targeted and evidence-based exploration of studies on storybook reading in the context of facilitating early mathematical skills.

The initial inclusion criteria for this review were developed based on the objective of exploring various methods of enriching storybooks to support early mathematical learning. Studies were included when they involved the use of embodied activities in whatever way ever—whether through physical interaction, augmented reality, or virtual reality. The rationale for including augmented and virtual reality is that these technologies can simulate embodied experiences by allowing children to interact with digital objects in a way that mimics physical manipulation, thus engaging the same cognitive and movement processes involved in embodied interactions.

We searched the literature by reviewing peer-reviewed articles in databases such as ERIC (Ovid), Scopus, PsycArticles, and Web of Science. The search used the terms "picture book*", "storybook*", "book*", "numeracy book*", "counting book*", "dialogic reading", "Math-related fiction", "shared book reading", "storytelling", as well as the following

terms related to key mathematical concepts and skills "math*", "count*", "num*", "arithm*", "algebra", "numeracy", "mathematics concept*", "problem-solving", and "geometr*". To consider potential enrichment of the storybooks we used the following search terms "enrich*", "exten*", "amend*", "embodi*", "gesture*", "Augmented Reality" and to specify our target group, we included the terms "preschool*," "pre-school*," "kindergarten*," "primary school*," "child*," "early childhood", "childhood", and "early year*". This search yielded about 14,000 articles. We focused on English-language, peer-reviewed articles due to their availability, accessibility, and quality, with no specific time period restrictions. Our search was completed on October 14, 2024.

All authors collectively undertook a literature search and documented relevant studies. During collaborative sessions, we eliminated potential duplicates and assessed the inclusion criteria for the identified articles. We excluded articles that were identified as nonunique records or failed to align with the final inclusion criteria: intervention or user study, including control groups or conditions, kindergarten to primary school children, math-related content, belonging to enrichment category: motor skills, enactment, augmented reality, virtual reality, gestures. Subsequently, each author individually reviewed the abstracts of the 58 remaining studies (see Fig. 2), removing articles that did not meet the predetermined inclusion criteria. Disagreements were resolved in joint discussions. Following this selection of articles, we acquired the full texts of the selected articles. After a thorough evaluation, we conducted an additional screening round, resulting in a final count of 11 articles. The articles finally considered in our scoping review are listed in Table 1 and summarized below.

2.1. Review of the studies

In reviewing the literature on enhancing storybook reading experiences for mathematics learning, we observed that the approaches can be placed into two broad categories. One involves the enrichment of storybooks through physical interactions—the use of motor skills and gestures emphasizing more tangible, hands-on experiences within the adult-child environment. The other approach explores the integration of digital elements into traditional storytelling or technology-driven advancements such as augmented reality and wearables. Recognizing this dichotomy, we organize our review thematically and chronologically.

Enrichment of Storybooks through Physical Interactions: Studies in this category primarily examine the enhancement of storybook reading using physical interactions such as gestures and manipulatives. Two studies by Casey et al. [39] examined how storytelling could enhance geometry learning for kindergarteners. Both studies used *Tan and the Shape Changer*, a story where children solved geometric puzzles

Fig. 2. PRISMA Flow Chart reflecting the process of identifying relevant studies to be included in the present scoping review.

to help characters, incorporating interactive elements like puppets, songs, and movements in the intervention groups.

The first study involved 155 children from a diverse suburban community, 80 girls and 75 boys. The intervention group received storytelling-integrated geometry lessons focusing on part-whole relations (e.g., combining isosceles triangles to form larger shapes) and foundational skills, such as identifying shapes, combining and partitioning shapes, and understanding spatial relations (e.g., recognizing how two triangles can form a square or identifying missing parts of a shape). The control group followed the standard math curriculum without supplemental activities. Girls in the intervention group improved significantly on near-transfer tasks (e.g., solving puzzles with isosceles triangles). Boys showed similar gains across groups, suggesting they may benefit from other spatial activities outside the intervention.

The second study involved 63 children from low-income urban schools. The intervention group received storytelling-integrated geometry lessons (same as study 1) and the control group geometry-only lessons (same content but without the storytelling component). Both covered the same content, but the storytelling group experienced it within a narrative. The storytelling group outperformed the geometry-only group on both near-transfer (e.g., similar puzzles) and far-transfer tasks (e.g., new puzzles). Girls especially excelled at far-transfer tasks, highlighting the potential of storytelling to promote broader knowledge application. Storytelling-integrated geometry lessons effectively supported spatial reasoning, especially for girls. Embedding math in meaningful narratives helps engage learners and foster deeper understanding.

Overall, both studies provide empirical support for the integration of storytelling in teaching geometry, highlighting its significant benefits, especially for girls, and indicating its potential as a valuable educational

strategy for diverse and economically disadvantaged populations.

Vandermaas-Peeler et al. [40] demonstrated how involving children in manipulation-based activities while or after reading storybooks improved their ability to understand and apply mathematical concepts. In their study, they observed thirty-seven families with a four-year-old child (13 low-income). Two types of numeracy interactions between parent and child were investigated: socio-cultural numeracy exchanges (e.g., about the value of money or number via routine activities, such as shopping or cooking) and more specific mathematics exchanges (e.g., counting, quantity, or size comparison). They used a storybook by Rosemary Wells, *Bunny Money* [41], which describes bunny siblings Ruby and Max as they use 'bunny money' to shop for gifts for their grandmother's birthday. The play materials included a grocery store with pretend food, 'bunny money,' and cooking materials. Parents were asked to rate the familiarity and enjoyment of the storybook, while children should rate their enjoyment of engaging in the storybook.

Results indicated that high-income parents engaged in more mathematics exchanges during both reading and play compared to low-income parents, though there were no differences in the initiation of socio-cultural numeracy exchanges (such as explaining the value and use of money or a credit card). Additionally, there were more mathematics exchanges (such as quantity and mathematics operations) with girls than boys during the reading activity. Also, parents reported that children were familiar with the toys for playing, and both parents and children enjoyed the storybook reading and playing, with girls reporting higher levels of enjoyment than boys. The findings suggest the importance of parent engagement in numeracy-related discourse in the context of daily routines to augment young children's numeracy development. Furthermore, when play materials are connected to the narrative of a storybook, it is likely to enhance and reinforce numeracy-

Table 1
Summary of reviewed articles (in alphabetical order).

First Author	Year	Study Type	Enhancement	Mathematics Content	N	Age	Key Findings	Math Measure	Outcome Types	Control Group
Björklund	2023	Observation	Tangibles, Gestures	Identifying, comparing numbers	27	1–3	Gestures helped connect representations	Video observations, gesture coding	Math behavior	No
Casey	2008	Quasi-Experiment	Tangibles, Storytelling	Geometry, part-whole	155 (80 girls)	5–6	Storytelling improved geometry skills, especially in girls;	Pre-post test (geometry tasks)	Math performance	Yes
Eason	2018	Experiment	Tangibles	Fractions, part-whole	72 (14 per condition)	4–5	More math talk in guided/formal learning vs unguided play	Observation of math talk	Math talk	Yes
Glenberg	2012	Experiment	Manipulation, Imagery	Word Problems	97 (39 CG)	8–10	Manipulation and imagery reduced irrelevant info use; improved problem-solving	Pre-post test (word problems)	Math performance + math behavior	Yes
Jylänki	2023	Intervention	Motor Skills, Gestures	Relational, Comparative	18	4.5	Gestures improved numeracy and motor skills	Teacher ratings, observation (motor & math)	Math performance	Yes
Kim	2020	UX	Technology; Wearables	n/a	11	3–9	Prototype stage, no learning outcome.	qualitative feedback	Engagement	No
Li	2019	UX	Technology; AR	Addition, Subtraction	20	7–8	AR increased motivation for math tasks	Observation, no formal assessment	Motivation	No
Lubis	2022	Quasi-Experiment	Technology; AR	n/a	60 (30 CG)	10	AR decreased math anxiety	Math anxiety (pre-post)	Anxiety	Yes
Vandermaas-Peeler	2009	Observation	Tangibles	Counting, Numbers, Finances	37	4	Play materials enhanced mathematics talk	Video coding of math-related talk	Math talk	No
Wangid	2020	Quasi-Experiment	Technology; AR	n/a	348	7–8	AR decreased math anxiety	Math anxiety scale (pre-post)	Anxiety	Yes
Zainudin	2020	Prototype	Technology; AR	n/a	n/a	7–8	Motivation improved	Motivation questionnaire (pre-post)	Motivation	Yes

Note. n/a = no information provided; N = sample size; CG = control group; AR = augmented reality. Math behavior = observable, informal indicators of mathematical thinking in young children, such as pointing, gesturing, comparing quantities, or using spatial language. In Björklund & Palmér [37], these behaviors were video-recorded and analyzed, while in Jylänki et al. [38], they were assessed through structured teacher observations.

related play activities.

The research by Glenberg et al. [12] involved 97 third and fourth-grade participants (aged 8 to 10) from a school where each child had access to laptops. The study explored the impact of the "Moved by Reading" condition, employing embodied simulation strategies such as Picture Manipulation and Imagination Manipulation. Picture Manipulation required children to simulate sentence content by moving corresponding pictures, while Imaging Manipulation involved mentally imagining the actions described in the text. The children read narrative and expository-like texts, and the mathematics story problems within them varied in complexity. Results showed that the intervention significantly reduced the inclusion of irrelevant numerical information in solution procedures. This suggests that teaching fundamental reading comprehension strategies, specifically including embodied simulation, can effectively enhance mathematics problem-solving skills.

In an experimental study, Eason & Ramani [42] investigated 72 dyads of 4–5-year-olds and their parents to evaluate differences in the quantity and quality of parent and child mathematics talk during three different fractions-related activities. 1) unguided play: in this condition, parents received wooden food toys partitioned into different numbers of pieces, which could be attached together by Velcro, a wooden knife, cutting board, and four plates. Parents were asked to play as when they were at home. 2) guided play: in this condition, parents were given the same materials along with a storybook about four friends having a picnic which included six questions to engage children in exploring the wooden toys and how the food could be shared fairly. 3) formal learning: in this condition, the same materials were provided except that the toy food was glued together and not separated, but the partitions were still visible. Instead of a storybook, the parents received worksheets with the

same questions as in the storybook in the guided play condition. This condition aimed to replicate a formal learning experience while limiting the children's active manipulation.

Results indicated that in the formal learning and guided play condition, parents used a higher percentage of mathematics talk as well as a greater variety of mathematics words compared to unguided play. However, parents in the formal learning condition also used a higher percentage of mathematics talk, and a greater variety of mathematics terms than those in guided play. Nevertheless, parents perceived guided play as more enjoyable for both them and their children. This suggests that this condition might be a promising way to promote mathematics engagement at home, given its capacity to elicit increased mathematics talk while maintaining a positive and enjoyable learning experience. As such, the study indicated that storybook reading enhanced by manipulable toys can foster enhanced early mathematics learning compared to unguided play (or only toys).

Björklund and Palmér [37] aimed to better understand how to design and use pictures and narratives for numerical learning. Seventy-three video documentation of reading sessions of three teachers with 27 toddlers (1–3 years of age) over the course of three semesters were analyzed with a focus on designing pictures to discern numbers with a special focus on cardinality and part-whole relations. In Björklund & Palmér [43]'s previous design, four design principles were explicitly followed: i) the mathematics content makes sense to children; ii) the mathematics content is meaningful and relevant to the age of children with a wide construct of numbers; iii) the mathematics content is presented visually in the pictures and iv) experiencing variation in learning situation. In contrast, the storybook in this study was designed to keep the content simple (i.e., a dog playing with building blocks) with no

scripted story to evaluate how teachers would make use of gestures or props that may strengthen the possibility for the children to connect within and between representations when reading the book to children. By analyzing the videos, three main themes of learning—identifying numbers, comparing numbers, and operating on numbers—were identified. With respect to the extension of the visually presented content (the storybook), teachers mostly used gestures, such as pointing or circling, often combined with counting words, to direct the child's attention. Furthermore, counting words and finger patterns were an additional means of expanding visual storybook content. Teachers also incorporated physical props, such as building blocks, into reading sessions to extend the storybooks. These findings contribute to our understanding that complementing illustrations with different representations and gestures seem to improve children's numerical learning.

Jylänki et al. [38] investigated the impact of the MovEN intervention program on improving early numeracy skills in preschoolers by combining storybook reading with motor skill practice. With a focus on children performing low in early numeracy, the research included two studies each investigating 18 children. The intervention involved teachers reading 5 storybooks with rich mathematics language (e.g. Harold and the Purple Crayon) using the dialogic reading approach and thus discussing numerical concepts with the children. After reading and discussion, children were trained in motor exercises related to the stories (e.g., gestures to indicate small, near, more, etc. while re-telling the story). Subsequently, the children were trained in general motor skills (locomotion, balance, throwing, catching, etc.), and there was a recap of the words learned related to math. Study I, utilizing a within-subject repeated-measures design, showed significant, sustained improvements in early numeracy and motor skills, though not in symbolic magnitude processing. Study II, a quasi-experimental design with an intervention and control group, demonstrated improvements in both groups, with the intervention group exhibiting a larger effect size, particularly in motor skill performance. The integration of storybook reading with motor skill practice holds promise for fostering early numeracy skills in preschoolers.

Enrichment of Storybooks through Digital Elements: Studies falling into this category focus on the use of digital tools like augmented reality to enhance storybook reading.

Li, van der Spek, Hu, and Feijs [44] developed an augmented reality game where animated animals appear on a mathematics textbook. Children scan the book with a smartphone to find animals that await their assistance for mathematics exercises. Once the relationship bar is full, children receive mathematics exercises, with immediate feedback on correct or incorrect answers, accompanied by rewards or encouraging messages from the animals. User studies with 20 7 to 8-year-old children in China and 18 in The Netherlands showed no difference in mathematics scores, but the augmented reality game received higher ratings for enjoyment, fun, and willingness to do mathematics exercises in free time. Further development involved testing screen touch and tangible interactions, with qualitative analysis suggesting potential boredom with screen touch and increased motivation with tangible interaction, despite it being more cumbersome.

In a recent paper, Zainudin & Ismail [45] outlined some initial ideas about designing interactive stories (e.g., integrating 3D pop-up and augmented reality features) by analyzing existing storybook application designs. The design is based on the evolutionary prototype model: requirement analysis, design, building prototypes, evaluation by customer, and final product. Some used interactive animation to teach simple mathematics concepts, some used augmented reality features to teach counting, some used 3D pop-up games in the middle of the story to teach fairy tales, and some designed a simple story with interactive features to teach geometry. To conclude, the authors suggest beginning with certain criteria to develop the storyline, such as clarity, short sentences, a topic to be taught, the age of the target children, the characters in the story, and a situation in which the mathematics concept can be learned. Since this study is still ongoing and the authors

are building a prototype model, there are no quantitative results yet.

Wangid et al. [46] examined the efficacy of augmented reality enhanced storybooks in mitigating mathematics anxiety among elementary school students. The research involved 348 fourth-grade students in Yogyakarta, Indonesia, selected using a cluster random sampling technique. The study employed a quantitative approach with a quasi-experimental pretest-posttest control group design. The Augmented Reality-assisted storybooks integrated cutting-edge technology, providing an interactive, 3D visualization experience that was assumed to enhance students' engagement and understanding of mathematics concepts and was designed to make mathematics learning more appealing. Compared to a control condition, the study revealed a significant reduction in mathematical anxiety among students who utilized Augmented Reality-assisted storybooks for learning (p -value < 0.05). The study demonstrated the potential of Augmented Reality-enhanced storybooks to ameliorate mathematics anxiety, offering a novel strategy to enhance mathematics education in elementary school.

Kim et al. [11] conducted a user study focusing on Wearable Story—a novel interactive jacket designed for children aged 3 to 9. The wearable interface narrates the story comparable to an audiobook, with microcontrollers integrated into the clothing to detect tactile inputs. These were used to activate narrative prompts like voice instructions to enhance children's involvement with the story's content. The voice instructs children to participate in physical and imaginative activities related to the storyline, such as jumping or pretending to swing over a castle. The study involved 11 families recruited from an after-school program. Data collection methods included semi-structured interviews, questionnaires, and video-recorded observations. Results indicated that 10 out of 11 families responded positively during the needs analysis, and children generally showed a high level of engagement during the user study. They interacted actively with the system (talking to it), followed narrative instructions by searching for non-existent objects, and engaged in pretend play (e.g., swinging over imagined obstacles or jumping over a pillow as if it were a puddle). While the study provided valuable initial insights such as high engagement, positive reception, promotion of imagination, the integration of physical activity, and design feasibility, it acknowledges the need for further empirical analysis to deepen the understanding of children's engagement with wearable storytelling experiences. The authors mention that they are planning an intervention study. The conclusion suggests the potential utility of further exploration in the realm of wearable storytelling experiences for children.

A study by Lubis et al. [47] investigated the impact of augmented reality pictorial storybooks on reducing mathematics anxiety in elementary school students. Although only indirectly aligned with our primary focus on learning, it serves as an illustrative example. The research explored the effects of an Augmented Reality-enhanced pictorial storybook on the mathematics anxiety levels of elementary school students during mathematics learning. The study involved 60 fourth-grade students aged 10, selected through cluster random sampling. Thirty students in the experimental group were provided with a specially designed storybook containing barcodes. When scanned using a smartphone, these barcodes triggered three-dimensional images, aiding the students in comprehending mathematics concepts (e.g., the concept of angles in triangles was illustrated by virtually hoisting a flag), while the control group was not provided with the Augmented Reality-enhanced storybooks. The findings indicate that the experimental group experienced a significant reduction in mathematics anxiety from pre- to post-intervention compared to the control group, demonstrating the potential of Augmented Reality-enhanced materials in alleviating mathematics anxiety among elementary school students.

3. Discussion

Research indicated that the effectiveness of using storybooks for

facilitating early literacy skills in children can be significantly enhanced by dialogic features requiring children to interact with aspects of the story (e.g., [12]). In particular, embodied interactions were found to increase effectiveness. However, while we know that storybook reading is also effective in facilitating early mathematics learning, research on how to enrich mathematics storybook reading is scarce. Therefore, we aimed to review existing evidence on how to enrich mathematics storybook reading.

Upon thorough review, we observed two primary approaches. The studies following the first approach—focusing on hands-on, physical experiences within the adult-child environment—tended to report outcomes related to numerical learning. Storybooks, when enriched with motor skills engagement, enactment, and the use of tangible toys, can directly contribute to the development of early mathematical skills. In contrast, studies following the technology-driven approach—encompassing interactive narratives, Augmented Reality, and wearable technology—tended to report outcomes around increased engagement and reduction in mathematics anxiety. While these technologically enhanced storybooks may not directly impact numerical learning (or, at least, this was not measured by the studies), they play a role in fostering a positive attitude towards and enhancing overall engagement with mathematical concepts. This difference in the focus of measuring either educational outcomes or engagement may have to do with the difference in academic disciplines of the respective authors. Researchers from education tended to measure educational outcomes when evaluating storybooks as educational tools. In contrast, researchers in areas such as human-computer interaction may instead have focused more on tool usability and engagement. In the following, we will discuss these two approaches in turn.

3.1. Embodied interactions and learning outcomes

In the studies reviewed, the most common means of enriching mathematics storybooks involved the use of embodied interactions with the mathematics concepts covered in the narrative. This included incorporating movements referring to numerical concepts within the narrative (such as gestures for “far”, “small”, etc.) as in Jylänki et al.’s [38] MovEN intervention program. In particular, the latter involved combining dialogic story reading with subsequent re-telling of the story by the children while using the respective gestures, followed by a motor skill practice (locomotion, balance, manual dexterity), creating a multisensory experience to further facilitate the acquisition of early numeracy skills. Re-playing/re-enacting a storyline or manipulating objects mentioned in a storybook after the respective part of a storybook was read to children was also found to foster mathematics language and understanding [40]. This aligns with findings by Van den Heuvel-Panhuizen & Elia [19], who observed that mathematics storybook reading supports reflective discussions between adults and children about mathematical ideas.

Similarly, the studies by Casey et al. [39] also emphasize the importance of hands-on, manipulative-based learning within a storytelling context. Their intervention involved the use of interactive teaching techniques such as puppets, chants, and movements, directly integrating these elements into a meaningful narrative to teach geometry. This approach not only allowed children to engage physically with the mathematical concepts, but also facilitated cooperative problem-solving within the story, reinforcing their understanding of geometry. Such approaches may be particularly effective for engaging young learners in spatial reasoning tasks. Furthermore, their second study demonstrated that storytelling, when combined with geometry instruction, was more effective than geometry instruction alone, in particular for students from disadvantaged backgrounds.

An additional opportunity for children to actively manipulate toys resembling storybook objects was observed to enhance mathematics language as demonstrated by [42]. This proved more effective than solely manipulating toys that have potential mathematics content (i.e.,

wooden toy foods pieces put together with Velcro). The effectiveness approached that of a formal learning condition where such toys were glued together to eliminate the manipulation component. Similarly, just manipulating a picture on a computer screen or the mere imagination thereof effectively enhances mathematics problem-solving skills [12]. Another example of embodied enrichment includes the specific use of gestures in storytelling, as highlighted by Björklund and Palmér’s [37] study. In particular, they designed a storybook that showed one simple action (e.g., a dog playing with building blocks), and found that teachers used gestures to strengthen children’s connections within and between representations of numbers (e.g., for three blocks, the gestures used would be counting the number three and pointing at the three blocks in the storybook individually). Similarly, the Wearable Story jacket, studied by Kim et al. [11], provides instructional prompts, inviting children to act out movements that follow the storyline, such as jumping over an object when the story mentioned jumping over a pond.

3.2. Digital enhancement and engagement

As mentioned earlier, the studies incorporating technology placed particular emphasis on affective components such as engagement, motivation, and the alleviation of mathematics anxiety, thereby indirectly contributing to potential improvement of mathematics learning. Examples include augmented reality features in interactive stories to enhance engagement [45], augmented reality features to alleviate mathematics anxiety [46,47], and an augmented reality game [44] to increase motivation, illustrating technology’s role in cultivating positive affective attitudes toward mathematics learning. Kim and colleagues’ [48] investigation of the Wearable Story further suggests that technology-infused wearables can boost engagement in story-based mathematics activities. However, it is essential to consider these findings with caution, given that some studies following this approach lack quantitative results and present varying degrees of information quality, requiring a nuanced interpretation of their findings.

Taken together, embodied interactions such as gestures, through Augmented Reality, and acting out movements or actions have the potential to enhance mathematics storybook reading in a manner previously observed in research on storybooks for literacy learning. While some of these approaches can improve children’s numerical learning (e.g., using gestures, re-enactment of story aspects, manipulating toys, etc.), others seem to be effective in increasing motivation and engagement or reduce mathematics anxiety (e.g., augmented reality and wearables). As such, we note that the enhancements explored may not only facilitate mathematical skill development but also other aspects such as mathematical reflections and discussions [19], engagement [48], or affective reactions [46,47]. Additionally, research by Casey et al. [39] further underscores the importance of integrating storytelling with direct mathematical instruction, particularly for girls.

3.3. Limitations and perspectives

When interpreting the results of the present scoping review, there are some limitations to consider. First, it is important to consider that across the reviewed studies, engagement and motivation were important topics, but their definitions and measurement varied considerably. Engagement was systematically measured only in a few cases. For example, Gibson et al. [24] asked parents to rate their child’s engagement during daily reading sessions, providing a standardized measure of attentional and behavioral involvement. In contrast, other studies inferred engagement from behavioral observations or qualitative descriptions. For instance, Kim et al. [11] reported increased engagement based on movement tracking and participation in embodied storytelling tasks, while Jylänki et al. [38] and Casey et al. [39] described children as “interested” or “eager,” without formal assessment.

Moreover, motivation was also addressed inconsistently. Only Zainudin and Ismail [45] directly measured learning motivation using a

self-report questionnaire, finding significantly higher motivation scores in children using augmented reality-enhanced storybooks compared to a control group. In other studies, motivation rather was inferred from expressions of enjoyment or preference, such as in Li et al. [44], where children favored interactive digital storybooks, or in Eason and Ramani [42], where children showed a preference for storybook-based activities over worksheets. While engagement and motivation were frequently cited as benefits of storybook-based interventions, their operationalization remains inconsistent. As such, future studies should clarify these constructs and adopt validated instruments to better understand their role in supporting early mathematics learning.

Furthermore, while the present review focused on storybook-based interventions, it is important to consider how these compare to other playful learning activities, such as board games for instance. Comparable to board games, storybooks can promote engagement and learning by creating contexts that invite active participation. While both formats can foster engagement and interaction, storybooks typically embed mathematical content more in a narrative structure, which supports meaning-making and retention [19]. In particular, narratives can help children associate abstract mathematical concepts with familiar contexts, potentially enhancing both cognitive and emotional engagement (e.g. [22]). In contrast, board games emphasize more rule-based interaction and repeated practice which was found to foster early mathematical skill such as counting and conceptual subitizing (e.g., [49]). At the same time, they also help support other skills such as cognitive flexibility and executive functions. In this sense, Vita-Barrull et al. [50] showed that a board game intervention improved both executive functioning and mathematics outcomes. As such both approaches involve embodied and motivational elements but differ in cognitive focus and may thus be complementary in early mathematics education.

4. Conclusion

This paper has explored how storybook reading for mathematics can be supported and enhanced, emphasizing the potential of embodied learning experiences. The key points discussed underscore the effectiveness of mathematics storybooks in promoting various mathematics skills, from numeracy to geometry, and the evolution of traditional storybooks through enriching elements such as gestures, motor skill practice, and Augmented Reality.

A significant takeaway from the discussions is the potential of embodied experiences in enhancing mathematics learning through storybooks. Glenberg's studies on simulation and the "Moved by Reading" method nicely illustrated the critical role of bodily experiences in reading comprehension and solving text problems in mathematics [12]. Additionally, the intersection of embodied actions and numerical cognition, as demonstrated by significant associations of fine motor skills and early numerical skills further highlights the potential of embodied experiences in enhancing children's mathematics understanding [29–31,51,52].

The implications of these findings are relevant for educators and researchers alike. Educators could leverage the insights from this article to design mathematics storybook experiences that integrate embodied learning activities. Strategies such as incorporating gestures in storytelling, as seen in the work by Björklund and Palmér [43] and Jylänki and colleagues [38], or the use of manipulatives resembling objects in the storybook to be dealt with as studied by Eason & Ramani [42] and Vandermaas-Peeler and colleagues [40] offer approaches to better engage children in meaningful mathematics learning experiences. Additionally, the success of the "Moved by Reading" enrichment approach suggests that incorporating embodied actions, such as acting out components of the story using manipulatives, can significantly improve story recall and vocabulary acquisition [13] with first evidence suggesting this beneficial effect generalizes to mathematics concepts. Casey et al.'s [39] studies further support the integration of storytelling with mathematical content, particularly in geometry.

For researchers, the call for further exploration of diverse avenues of enriching mathematics storybooks is crucial. The studies reviewed, as well as Op't Eynde et al.'s (2023) literature review on the effectiveness of storybook reading for learning mathematics highlight the need for more comprehensive investigations into non-verbal communication, complex factor associations, and intervention studies to better understand the underlying working mechanisms on how embodied learning experiences contribute to mathematics development in children.

Enriching storybooks in various ways, including the integration of digital media, Augmented Reality, and interactive designs, opens exciting possibilities for the future. The reviewed studies make for a limited but promising foundation for further research in evaluating the effectiveness of these enrichments in mathematics storybook reading. As technology continues to evolve, there is a need for ongoing investigations into how emerging technologies, such as augmented and virtual reality and wearables, can be harnessed to create immersive and impactful mathematics learning experiences for young learners.

The review of literature presented in this article underscores the dynamic interplay between storybook reading, embodied cognition, and early mathematics development. Going from traditional storybooks to enriched, interactive experiences can broaden the horizons of mathematics learning for young children. As educators and researchers continue to collaborate, innovate, and explore, the potential for enhancing mathematics learning through storybooks remains an exciting space for exploration, promising a future where every child can experience a captivating mathematical journey through the pages of a well-crafted and enriched storybook.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Ethical statement

This scoping review is based solely on previously published literature and did not involve the collection of new data from human participants. Therefore, ethical approval and informed consent were not required.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Venera Gashaj: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Dragan Trninić:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Ouhao Chen:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Korbinian Moeller:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest related to this work.

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